

Dynamic Handover via AI-assisted Signal Quality Prediction in 6G Multi-RAT Networks

Maria Lamprini A. Bartsioka*, Anastasios Giannopoulos*, Sotirios Spantideas*, Panagiotis Trakadas*

**R&D Department, Four Dot Infinity, Athens, Greece*

Emails: mbarts@fourdotinfinity.com, angianno@fourdotinfinity.com, sospanti@fourdotinfinity.com, ptrak@fourdotinfinity.com

Abstract—The emerging paradigm of 6G multiple Radio Access Technology (multi-RAT) networks, where cellular and Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) transmitters coexist, requires reliable mobility decisions under fast channel dynamics. Handover in multi-RAT deployments is still reactive, relying on instantaneous measurements and threshold events. This work proposes a Machine Learning (ML)-assisted Predictive Conditional Handover (P-CHO) framework based on short-horizon signal quality forecasts. We present a generalized P-CHO sequence workflow orchestrated by a RAT Steering Controller, which standardizes data collection, parallel per-RAT predictions, hysteresis-enabled conditions, and CHO execution. Considering a realistic multi-RAT environment, we train RAT-aware Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks to forecast the signal quality indicators of mobile users along randomized trajectories. The proposed models are trained and evaluated under 6G and IEEE 802.11 WiFi integrated coverage. We study the impact of hyperparameter tuning of LSTM models under different settings, and compare direct multi-step versus recursive P-CHO. Comparisons against baseline predictors are also carried out. Finally, the proposed P-CHO is tested under soft and hard handover settings, showing that hysteresis-enabled P-CHO scheme reduces handover by 40%, eliminating ping-pong events. Overall, the proposed P-CHO framework can enable accurate, low-latency, and proactive handovers suitable for ML-assisted handover steering in 6G multi-RAT deployments.

Index Terms—6G, WiFi, Handover, Machine Learning, Mobility Control, Multi-RAT Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Fifth-generation (5G) and beyond (B5G) communication networks are being deployed worldwide to address the growing demands for massive device connectivity, high capacity, ultra-low latency, and seamless communication across diverse scenarios [1]. A key architectural approach to meet these requirements is the deployment of heterogeneous networks (HetNets), classified into two categories: (i) those integrating multiple Radio Access Technologies (multi-RATs), and (ii) those comprising heterogeneous equipment types. Such architectures have been progressively incorporated into Third-Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) specifications starting from Release 11 [2]. In this work, the focus is on multi-RAT environments that enable the coexistence of B5G New Radio (NR) cellular infrastructures with complementary technologies such as Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) [3], [4]. Modern User

Equipments (UEs) support such dual-connectivity scenarios, typically prioritizing WiFi to minimize cellular data charges. However, this leads to throughput degradation in areas with obstacles. To overcome this, handover mechanisms are employed to dynamically switch between WiFi and cellular networks [5].

Traditional handover mechanisms between different RATs in current 5G/NR systems are typically event-driven and rely on instantaneous measurements of the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) [6]. Although conventional methods are simple and computationally efficient, they often result in suboptimal Quality of Service (QoS), especially in dynamic HetNets. Conditional Handover (CHO), standardized in 3GPP Release 16 [7], pre-configures one or more target cells together with execution conditions. The final handover is executed once those conditions are met, reducing command latency and improving reliability under fast fading and blockage. However, both conventional and CHO remain fundamentally reactive, since decisions are taken when thresholds are crossed, not based on forecasted link quality. Recently, Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) have emerged as promising enablers for intelligent mobility management, aiming to enable proactive handover decisions [8], [9]. Their ability to learn complex patterns makes them suitable for predicting multi-source wireless signal quality. Furthermore, ML-based mobility policies can simultaneously exploit UE measurements, environmental conditions, and user-specific objectives, achieving a balance between connectivity and efficiency [10].

In this context, this paper proposes a Predictive CHO (P-CHO) framework that supports ML-assisted dynamic RAT selection under mobility and interference. The goal is to augment CHO with model-driven forecasts of near-future Signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) for candidate RATs, turning execution conditions from static thresholds into time-aware predicates. By anticipating short-term degradations (e.g. WiFi shadowing or inter-cellular interference), P-CHO enables earlier preparation of target links and smarter selection among RATs. Sequence models such as Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), are well-suited for this task because they can (i) capture temporal dependencies in radio dynamics, (ii) provide accurate predictions of UE measurements, and, finally, (iii) generate actionable predictions for mobility control and traffic steering. As main contributions of this work:

- We formalize P-CHO for sixth-generation (6G) multi-RAT networks, enabling proactive vertical and horizontal

This work was supported in part by UNITY-6G Project, funded by the European Union's HORIZON-JU-SNS-2024 program under Grant No 101192650 and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI); and in part by the 6G-Cloud Project funded from the European Union's HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023 program under Grant No 101139073.

handovers across Cellular and WiFi RATs.

- We implement a hybrid Cellular/WiFi HetNet simulator that generates mobility and channel-realistic datasets.
- We design and train RAT-specific SINR forecasting models, including bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) for 6G Cellular BSs and a lightweight LSTM for WiFi APs, producing next-step and multi-step SINR estimates along stochastic user trajectories.
- We embed the SINR predictors into a RAT Steering Controller that combines multi-source UE measurement reports, infers pre-trained models, and converts SINR forecasts into steering execution conditions.
- We benchmark the proposed LSTM-based signal predictors against other ML-based models and traditional autoregressive models, demonstrating consistent improvements under dynamic channels.

II. RELATED WORK

Mobility management in 5G/6G HetNets has drawn significant attention, particularly at the intersection of handover control and data-driven intelligence. Most existing studies analyze handover within 5G NR or across Long Term Evolution (LTE)–5G, with increasing interest in predictive policies leveraging sequence models. In [11], a deep residual matrix LSTM was proposed to predict future user locations and trigger handover when distance to the serving Base Station (BS) exceeds a threshold. The method achieved increased handover success rate and reduced latency, outperforming Reinforcement Learning (RL) and Adaptive Cell Selection Algorithm (ACSA). A complementary direction was taken in [10], where an LSTM predicts the probability that each neighboring cell will have the highest Received Signal Strength Power (RSSP), formulating handover as a multi-class classification problem. Evaluated in a simulated industrial 5G setup, it reduced radio link failures and mitigated ping-pong effects. While compelling, the approaches were confined to intra-5G scenarios and did not consider multi-RAT interactions.

Learning-based policy optimization has also been explored. The authors in [12] studied dense HetNets with a deep Q-learning strategy that selects candidate BSs per time slot to optimize throughput, delay, and energy consumption. The RL method outperformed conventional A3 policies and decreased the energy usage, yet it did not explicitly forecast signal evolution. In a related concept, the authors in [13] extended the 3GPP-based CHO framework for millimeter-wave (mmWave) 5G with a deep neural model trained on geographical blockage patterns and RSSP sequences, producing next-cell probabilities. The reported accuracy (85%) and early-preparation success rate (98%) showcased the value of preparing handovers ahead of execution events, but the study remained single-RAT.

Regarding WiFi-related works, the study in [14] proposed a proactive cross-layer handover framework for Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs) that extracts network-layer features (RSSI, retransmissions, packet delay) to train ML classifiers distinguishing handover from non-handover states. The method reduces handover latency by approximately 200 ms

Fig. 1: Multi-RAT HetNet with a UE random-walk path.

and packet loss by over 30%. While effective, the study did not extend to heterogeneous cellular–WiFi coordination.

Works explicitly targeting multi-RAT are relatively sparse. One notable effort is [15], which combines a Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)-based throughput estimator with Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to learn discrepancies between estimated and actual throughput, thereby guiding the selection between 5G and WiFi transmitters and using Quick UDP Internet Connections (QUIC) scheme for migration. Nevertheless, the DRL agent requires periodical re-training once the network dynamics significantly change.

III. MULTI-RAT SYSTEM MODEL

A. System Overview

We consider a heterogeneous multi-RAT environment representative of B5G/6G deployments. The network comprises wide-area cellular BSs and overlapping short-coverage WiFi Access Points (APs), with mobile UEs traverse predefined paths within the coverage area as illustrated in Fig. 1. We define the following sets: (i) Set of BSs $S_{BS} = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{N_{BS}}\}$, (ii) Set of APs $S_{AP} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{N_{AP}}\}$, (iii) Set of UEs $S_{UE} = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{N_{UE}}\}$, and (iv) Set of UE paths $S_T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{N_T}\}$.

Two link types are considered, including (i) $L_{b,u}$ for cellular BS-UE communication and (ii) $L_{a,u}$ for AP-UE communication. Each link employs a RAT-specific channel model. For $L_{b,u}$, the received power accounts for large-scale path loss, small-scale fading, and co-channel interference from neighboring BSs. A generic distance-based attenuation is defined: $G(d) = K \cdot d^{-\alpha}$ where d is the BS–UE distance, α is the large-scale path loss exponent, and K is a scaling constant [16]. Small-scale fading is modeled as Rician to capture both Line-of-Sight (LoS) and non-LoS (NLoS) components. For a certain UE, let h denote the complex fading coefficient experienced over the serving link, and h_i denote the same for the interfering link i . The instantaneous cellular SINR is then expressed as:

$$\text{SINR}_{6G} = \frac{P_t \cdot |h|^2}{\sum_{i \in I} P_{t,i} \cdot |h_i|^2 + N_0 \cdot B} \quad (1)$$

where I is the set of interfering BSs, P_t ($P_{t,i}$) is the serving (cellular interferer's i) BS transmit power, N_0 is the spectral density of the noise power and B is the link bandwidth. The channel model of WiFi links $L_{a,u}$ follows an IEEE 802.11 channel model [17] that captures short-range indoor hotspot communications reflecting multipath and wall penetration losses: $PL(d) = PL(d_0) + 10 \cdot \gamma \cdot \log_{10} \frac{d}{d_0} + \sum_j L_j$ where $PL(d_0)$ stands for the reference path loss at distance $d_0 = 1$ m, γ is the indoor path loss exponent, and L_j represents additional loss due to obstacle j [17]. Small-scale fading and interference are omitted, resulting in:

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{WiFi}} = \frac{P_t \cdot |h|^2}{N_0 \cdot B} \quad (2)$$

UEs move along predefined two-dimensional (2D) trajectories $t \in S_T$ with constant speed. Trajectories are selected to span diverse directions, turning points, and RAT overlaps, thereby inducing varied sequences of serving RATs.

B. Handover Decision Problem Elements

Given a trajectory t and the network state at discrete time k , let \mathbf{x}_k denote the feature vector. The goal is to learn the following signal quality predictors:

$$\hat{s}_{k+\tau}^{(r)} = f^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}_k), \quad r \in \{S_{BS} \cup S_{AP}\}, \tau \in \{1, \dots, H\}, \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{s}_{k+\tau}^{(r)}$ is the predicted signal quality indicator for time instance $k + \tau$ and RAT r , $f^{(r)}$ is the learned function for RAT r that maps historical to future signal quality metrics, and τ is the forecasting horizon. Predictions $\hat{s}_{k+\tau}^{(r)}$ estimate short-horizon signal quality for each RAT using a historical feature vector \mathbf{x}_k of SINR_{6G} values (for cellular BSs) and SNR_{WiFi} values (for WiFi APs). At each step k , the RAT steering controller selects the target serving RAT as:

$$r_k^* = \arg \max_r \hat{s}_{k+\tau}^{(r)} \quad (4)$$

by combining all transmitters' predicted signals and selecting the best-SINR provider. The final decision can be conditioned by rule-based policies using multi-step predictors $\{\hat{s}_{k+\tau}^{(r)}\}_{\tau=1}^H$.

IV. ML-ASSISTED PROACTIVE HANDOVER

A. Network Simulator and Dataset Construction

Obtaining recent, real, and authenticated communication traces is challenging due to privacy policies and personal data regulations. Yet, ML/DL models require structured data for training and evaluation. To this end, we developed a Python-based simulator for the 5G/WiFi HetNet that represents the targeted communication environment and exports model-ready sequential datasets. As outlined in Section III-A, we develop a simulator that establishes communication between all available RAT endpoints and the UE while the latter moves along a predefined trajectory $t \in S_T$. For each trajectory, and at each discrete time index k , the simulator evaluates metrics for all $r \in R$, where $R \triangleq S_{BS} \cup S_{AP}$. Specifically, for every time instance of the mobility path and BS/AP candidate, the simulator

computes the RSSI, the SINR, and the achieved throughput (denoted as TP). The resulting raw time series are stored as tuples $M_r^t[k] = (\text{ID}_t, \text{RSSI}_r[k], \text{SINR}_r[k], \text{TP}_r[k])$, where ID_t is the identifier of trajectory t . The multi-source timeseries are temporally aligned, ensuring that for each k , measurements across RATs refer to the same UE position/sample.

To create input-output combinations for subsequent model training, the raw sequences are then segmented into overlapping windows of fixed length W . For node r and time index k , the input feature vector is:

$$\mathbf{x}_r[k] = [M_r^t[k - W + 1], \dots, M_r^t[k]], \forall t \in S_T \quad (5)$$

where $M_r^t[k]$ is the metric report tuple for node r when UE follows trajectory t , and is used to make a prediction at time k . This means that the model receives a history window of the W previous metric report tuples and predicts the one-step-ahead target, which is the upcoming metric tuple of the next time instance, i.e., $y_r[k] = M_r^t[k + 1]$.

The dataset is organized in a tabular form with columns ID_t , r , $\mathbf{x}_r[k]$, and $y_r[k]$, and exported into two separate (`.csv`) files for model training purposes. We train two models, including one for cellular BSs samples and one for APs samples. Standard sequence-model preprocessing steps are applied to ensure consistent scaling and robust evaluation.

B. ML Model Architecture for Signal Quality Prediction

We employ LSTM networks to forecast short-horizon signal quality for candidate BSs and APs. LSTMs are designed to capture long- and short-range temporal dependencies in sequential data and are therefore well suited to regress wireless signal evolution under mobility and time-varying interference.

Cellular BS predictor (BiLSTM): Cellular $L_{b,u}$ links exhibit richer temporal structure due to path-loss variation, blockage, and co-channel interference with adjacent BSs. To capture these dynamics, we use a deep BiLSTM. The first block processes the input window with two stacked LSTM layers in both forward and backward directions, enabling the model to exploit information across the entire input sequence. The recurrent output is then fed to a stack of fully-connected dense layers interleaved with ReLU activations and dropout to avoid overfitting. The output is a linear neuron that outputs a scalar next-step prediction $\hat{y}_r[k]$ for the selected metric.

WiFi AP predictor (lightweight LSTM): $L_{a,u}$ links typically exhibit shorter-range propagation with simpler temporal variability due to absence of interference. We therefore adopt a lightweight design with a single LSTM layer followed by one Dense layer that maps the last hidden state to the scalar output $\hat{y}_r[k]$. This design reduces computational and memory footprint while retaining sufficient accuracy.

Models are trained offline using root mean squared error (RMSE)-based and outlier-aware loss function. During online operation, a RAT Steering Controller queries the appropriate predictor to produce per-RAT short-horizon forecasts that feed the predictive P-CHO logic described below.

C. Proposed P-CHO Sequence Diagram

Recently 3GPP has introduced CHO, where preparation and execution are decoupled and execution occurs when a condition is satisfied [7]. We extend CHO to a P-CHO by deriving the condition from model-based SINR forecasts, thereby enabling proactive mobility.

Prediction-conditioned trigger: Let $\hat{s}_{\text{tar}}[k]$ and $\hat{s}_{\text{cur}}[k]$ denote the one-step-ahead predicted SINR (or SNR for WiFi) for the candidate target RAT and the current serving RAT, respectively. The execution condition is:

$$\Delta\text{QoS}[k] \triangleq \hat{s}_{\text{tar}}[k] - \hat{s}_{\text{cur}}[k] \geq \delta_{\text{QoS}} \quad (6)$$

where δ_{QoS} is a configurable threshold reflecting whether the handover is soft (low δ_{QoS}) or hard (high δ_{QoS}). By combining ML-based SINR prediction with handover thresholds, the system adopts a proactive and predictive behavior, allowing early preparation of handover events while regulating handover sensitivity [18].

End-to-end workflow (Fig. 2): It is composed by:

(1) Data Collection: The UE transmits a Measurement Report (MR) $M_r^t[k]$ via the serving BS/AP. The RAT Steering Controller stores it in an MR timeseries database and associates it with the UE's historical MR sequence to form inputs $\mathbf{x}_r[k]$ for each candidate RAT $r \in R$.

(2) SINR Prediction & Handover Decision: After the batch feature assembly operation, a parallel inference of SINR prediction models is performed in the Intelligent Module. Specifically, it infers the pre-trained predictors in parallel to obtain $\{\hat{s}^{(r)}[k]\}$ for $r \in R$. Optionally, model inference can be done on Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) to speed up the process. Afterwards, the Decision Module evaluates the condition in (6) for each candidate. If the condition holds for some $r^* \in R$ (target BS/AP), it issues a P-CHO decision toward r^* . Otherwise, the UE remains on the serving RAT.

(3) Handover Execution (conditional): Following a 3GPP-compliant procedure, based on the decision, the serving node sends a Handover Request to the target r^* . The target node performs admission control (resource availability/QoS checks) and responds with Handover Request ACK on success. Then, the serving node issues Radio Resource Control (RRC) Reconfiguration to the UE with target parameters. Upon completion, the UE synchronizes to the target and a status notification with Sequence Numbers is transferred to confirm handover success.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We consider a heterogeneous multi-RAT Cellular/WiFi network with mobile users served by BSs or APs. As in the topology of Fig. 1, the cellular tier comprises two 6G NR BSs operating at 3.5 GHz with partially overlapping cells. Inter-cell interference is present near the cell edges. Within each BS coverage, two IEEE 802.11 APs operate at 2.4 GHz on orthogonal channels (no co-channel interference across APs, no BS-AP interference due to different frequency bands). A UE traverses the topology along predefined trajectories at a speed of 3 m/s. This Python-based link/system simulator generates

Fig. 2: Proposed three-stage P-CHO sequence callflows.

time-synchronized sequences of per-RAT measurements. The problem of SINR prediction is examined as a supervised regression problem. For each candidate RAT r , a sliding window of length W forms the input, and the next-sample value of the SINR forms the target (see (5)). A training/test set split of 80%/20% has been used in the training phase of all approaches, while the models were tuned via grid search on different hyperparameters to ensure optimal performance.

A. Prediction Error vs Look-back and Look-ahead Windows

Performance evaluation was conducted through a series of experiments under varying conditions and objectives. First, we examined the impact of the lookback window size W on SINR prediction error. As shown in Fig. 3, increasing the window generally improves performance. For BS models, the trend is consistent, with the best RMSE achieved at a window of $W_{BS} = 9$ past time steps. For AP models, the curve is U-shaped, indicating that long windows lead to overfitting. Thus, the optimal window was set at $W_{AP} = 7$.

Next, we investigated the effect of the number of trajectories available for each UE. In general, adding more random-walk paths in a fixed topology increases route overlap among UEs. This tends to degrade model ability to discriminate among paths and makes the SINR prediction task more confusing and difficult. As illustrated in Fig. 4, enlarging the training set with additional trajectories does not monotonically improve generalization. For BS models, RMSE remains relatively stable up to $N_T = 17$ trajectories and then increases sharply beyond $N_T = 20$. For AP models, error decreases until $N_T = 17$ trajectories (benefiting from added variability) but rises thereafter, suggesting SINR distribution shift. To ensure

Fig. 3: Prediction RMSE versus Look-back Window size W for (a) Cellular BSs model and (b) WiFi APs model, considering 35 available UE paths.

Fig. 4: Prediction RMSE versus the number of UE paths N_T for (a) Cellular BSs model and (b) WiFi APs model.

a balance between adequate model performance and system stochasticity, we set the number of trajectories at $N_T = 20$ for the rest of the simulations. Note that, to increase model performance under large values of N_T , more dense LSTM models can be retrained.

We further evaluated the predictive capacity of the models by extending the forecast horizon τ to multiple time steps. Two approaches were considered: (i) *Direct multi-step*: the output layer is modified to emit $\tau = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$ steps jointly (see (3)), and the dataset is extended with targets $y_r[k] = M_r^t[k + \tau]$. This means that the prediction $y_r[k]$ made at time k refers to the estimated SINR value at time $k + \tau$, with the models directly trained using the SINR desired values for $k + \tau$. (ii) *Recursive prediction*: the original single-step models are retained and used recursively, feeding each predicted value back into the input window for the next step. As expected, considering the direct multi-step scheme, Fig. 5 confirms that increasing the lookahead horizon τ generally degrades accuracy due to higher uncertainty. However, the error increment is moderate (particularly for the AP model). This highlights that, if the look-ahead horizon is set to $\tau > 1$ for early decisions, we may expect a lower prediction accuracy, but the handover operation will be faster.

In Fig. 6, we contrast *direct multi-step* versus *recursive* forecasting at lookahead $\tau = 2$ and $\tau = 4$ time steps. Direct multi-step yields consistently lower RMSE, with only a mild increase when moving from $\tau = 2$ to $\tau = 4$ for both BS and AP models. In contrast, the recursive scheme incurs substantial RMSE by roughly $3\times$ for BSs and $4\text{--}5\times$ for APs, at the same horizon. Operationally, direct multi-

Fig. 5: Prediction RMSE versus Look-ahead Horizon τ in direct multi-step prediction for (a) Cellular BSs model and (b) WiFi APs model.

Fig. 6: Prediction RMSE of Direct and Recursive multi-step methods using Look-ahead horizons $\tau = 2$ and $\tau = 4$, separately for (a) Cellular BSs model and (b) WiFi APs model.

step training requires storing multiple horizon-specific models at RAT Steering Controller (per RAT), while the recursive scheme reuses only single-step models, reducing storage at the expense of accuracy.

B. Comparison against Baseline Signal Quality Predictors

Here we benchmark the proposed LSTM predictors against two classical baselines used for timeseries forecasting, including *Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)* [19] and *Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)* [20] models, under two N_T configurations. As shown in Fig. 7, for each model, the RMSE is higher for $N_T = 35$ due to the increased randomness in the mobility patterns. ARIMA exhibits the highest error across both RAT types and dataset scales, reflecting its stationary assumptions have limited ability to model non-linear interference and mobility effects in multi-RAT links. Moreover, XGBoost achieves slightly lower prediction error than LSTM only for low number of UE paths ($N_T = 17$), especially for AP prediction where short-range dynamics are simpler. However, its RMSE increases noticeably (relative to LSTM) when $N_T = 35$, indicating sensitivity to trajectory overlap and mobility randomness. In contrast, LSTM predictors (i) maintain a comparable error for low N_T and (ii) clearly exhibit the lowest RMSE as N_T increases. Overall, the comparative results of Fig. 7 suggest that the proposed P-CHO pipeline may use LSTM or XGBoost predictors when mobility patterns are deterministic, whereas LSTM models should be used for more stochastic UE mobility patterns.

Fig. 7: Prediction RMSE of different SINR predictors using different number of trajectories N_T for (a) Cellular BS models and (b) WiFi APs models.

C. Soft P-CHO versus Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO

At this point, we evaluate two alternative realizations of the proposed P-CHO framework:

- **Soft P-CHO:** The RAT Steering Controller triggers a handover when the next-step predicted gain (see (6)) over the serving RAT exceeds the QoS threshold at the current step. This means that the UE will switch from the current to the target serving transmitter if the following Soft P-CHO condition is met:

$$\Delta QoS[k+1] \triangleq \hat{s}_{tar}[k+1] - \hat{s}_{cur}[k+1] \geq \delta_{QoS} \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{s}_{tar}[k+1]$ and $\hat{s}_{cur}[k+1]$ refer to the predicted SINR values from the target and the current RAT (respectively) at time instance $k+1$.

- **Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO.** The same condition must hold for N consecutive steps (here $N \in \{2, 3\}$) before executing the handover. This gives the following Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO condition:

$$\Delta QoS[h] \geq \delta_{QoS}, \quad \forall h \in [k+1, k+N] \quad (8)$$

where h reflects a hysteresis variable denoting how many steps the target RAT must comply with (7).

To assess generalization capabilities, we test the handover performance of both P-CHO variants, considering an unseen testing UE trajectory that represents a complete path across the two BSs and three APs (see the selected UE path in Fig. 9).

In Fig. 8, we report the number of handover occurrences on the testing trajectory as a function of δ_{QoS} for both soft and hysteresis-enabled P-CHO variants. Increasing the P-CHO threshold from 0 dB to 3 dB reduces the total handovers for both schemes, reflecting more conservative decisions at higher margins and lower handover sensitivity levels. Across all P-CHO thresholds, the hysteresis-enabled scheme consistently yields fewer handovers than the soft P-CHO, demonstrating improved stability and reduced signaling without noticeable loss of connectivity along this path. In other words, hysteresis-enabled method adds short dwell-time guards to observe more stable and systematic handover gains, without reacting to transient advantages of a candidate RAT, which suggests a P-CHO behavior that suppresses ping-pong events.

Fig. 8: Number of Handover events as function of P-CHO Threshold δ_{QoS} for Soft and Hysteresis-enabled methods.

To visualize the handover behavior of both methods, Fig. 9 depicts the selected serving RAT decisions (color-coded) along the testing trajectory, separately for the Soft and Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO. Both schemes are set at a threshold of $\delta_{QoS} = 2.5$ dB. The actual best-SINR servers are shown in Fig. 9(a), where it is evident that the best-SINR node frequently varies along the UE path due to dynamic downlink conditions and mobility. In Fig. 9(b), we show the UE-node association derived by following the condition in (7), while Fig. 9(c) shows the best RAT selected by (8) for $N = 3$. Evidently, Soft P-CHO exhibits short dwell segments and five switches in the overlap regions between RATs (e.g., near the transitions AP3 \leftrightarrow BS2). This confirms its responsiveness but also its susceptibility to small transient SINR advantages, reflecting classic ping-pong behavior when ΔQoS varies around the threshold. Second, Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO maintains longer contiguous segments on the selected RAT and suppresses rapid back-and-forth changes around cell borders. Although this sometimes delays a switch, it eliminates non-beneficial changes caused by short fluctuations or prediction noise. Third, both policies converge to the same (and actual) serving RAT over most of the trajectory, indicating that prediction-conditioned triggers preserve the correct association pattern. As a result, the hysteresis enforces temporal consistency before execution, leading to fewer and more decisive handovers. This is translated into reduced signaling and a lower risk of service interruptions. Overall, a clear trade-off arises: Soft P-CHO maximizes reactivity to predicted gains, while Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO maximizes stability by filtering out short-term advantages. Selecting (δ_{QoS}, N) provides a practical way to tailor the mobility policy to the application needs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE EXTENSIONS

This paper introduces an ML-assisted conditional and dynamic handover framework for 6G multi-RAT deployments. The proposed scheme designs RAT-aware short-horizon SINR predictors and integrates them into a P-CHO workflow orchestrated by a RAT Steering Controller. Results show that (i) appropriate windowing improves accuracy, (ii) excessive

Fig. 9: The selected serving RAT along a UE trajectory, color-coded per RAT transmitter. (a) Association based on the actual best-SINR server. (b) Association by the Soft P-CHO decisions. (c) Association by the Hysteresis-enabled P-CHO decisions.

UE trajectory overlap makes predictions less accurate, and (iii) direct multi-step prediction for long-term forecasts outperforms recursive inference by more than 60%. Compared against ARIMA and XGBoost, the LSTM models deliver lower RMSE and degrade more gracefully as data complexity grows. Finally, the hysteresis-enabled P-CHO variant further reduced unnecessary handovers relative to the soft P-CHO.

Several directions can extend this work. The proposed multi-RAT system can be integrated in an Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) environment where predictors and P-CHO rules are deployed as xApps. Another extension is to jointly optimize prediction and policy via multi-objective control (QoS, energy, latency) or multi-agent RL for multi-UE coordination. Finally, to ensure low-latency inference at the edge, model compression or distillation techniques may be used.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. T. Spantideas, A. E. Giannopoulos, and P. Trakadas, "Smart mission critical service management: Architecture, deployment options, and experimental results," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 1108–1128, 2025.
- [2] G. T. S. Group, "Evolved universal terrestrial radio access (e-utra); mobility enhancements in heterogeneous networks," 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Tech. Rep. 3GPP TS 36.839 V11.0.0, 2012, release 11. [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org/DynaReport/36839.htm>
- [3] T. Sylla, L. Mendiboure, S. Maaloul, H. Aniss, M. A. Chalouf, and S. Delbruel, "Multi-connectivity for 5g networks and beyond: A survey," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 19, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/19/7591>
- [4] I. A. Bartsiokas, P. K. Gkonis, A. K. Papazafeiropoulos, D. I. Kaklamani, and I. S. Venieris, "Federated learning for 6g hetnets' physical layer optimization: Perspectives, trends, and challenges," *Encyclopedia of Information Science and Technology*, Sixth Edition, pp. 1–28, 2025.
- [5] W.-H. Yang, T. T. Phan, Y.-A. Chen, J.-X. Lin, and C.-Y. Li, "Smart handover between 5g and wi-fi over quic at network edge for maximizing throughput," in *2024 International Computer Symposium (ICS)*, 2024, pp. 127–132.
- [6] P. Satapathy and J. Mahapatro, "An adaptive context-aware vertical handover decision algorithm for heterogeneous networks," *Computer Communications*, vol. 209, pp. 188–202, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S014036642300227X>
- [7] G. T. S. Group, "5g; nr; nr and ng-ran overall description; stage-2," 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Tech. Rep. 3GPP TS 38.300 V16.4.0, 2021, release 16. [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org/DynaReport/38300.htm>
- [8] A. Giannopoulos, S. Spantideas, P. Trakadas, J. Perez-Valero, G. Garcia-Aviles, and A. S. Gomez, "Ai-driven self-healing in cloud-native 6g networks through dynamic server scaling," in *2025 IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 2025, pp. 43–48.
- [9] A. Almeida, P. Rito, S. Brás, F. C. Pinto, and S. Sargento, "A machine learning approach to forecast 5g metrics in a commercial and operational 5g platform: 5g and mobility," *Computer Communications*, vol. 228, p. 107974, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140366424003219>
- [10] A. Masri, T. Veijalainen, H. Martikainen, S. Mwanje, J. Ali-Tolppa, and M. Kajó, "Machine-learning-based predictive handover," in *2021 IFIP/IEEE International Symposium on Integrated Network Management (IM)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 648–652.
- [11] A. Baz, J. Logeshwaran, Y. Natarajan, and S. K. Patel, "Enhancing mobility management in 5g networks using deep residual lstm model," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 165, p. 112103, 2024.
- [12] Y. Song, S. H. Lim, and S.-W. Jeon, "Handover decision making for dense hetnets: A reinforcement learning approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 24 737–24 751, 2023.
- [13] C. Lee, H. Cho, S. Song, and J.-M. Chung, "Prediction-based conditional handover for 5g mm-wave networks: A deep-learning approach," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 54–62, 2020.
- [14] J. V. Cervantes-Bazán, A. D. Cuevas-Rasgado, L. M. Rojas-Cárdenas, S. Lazcano-Salas, F. García-Lamont, L. A. Soriano, J. d. J. Rubio, and J. Pacheco, "Proactive cross-layer framework based on classification techniques for handover decision on wlan environments," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 712, 2022.
- [15] W.-H. Yang, T. T. Phan, Y.-A. Chen, J.-X. Lin, and C.-Y. Li, "Smart handover between 5g and wi-fi over quic at network edge for maximizing throughput," in *2024 International Computer Symposium (ICS)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 127–132.
- [16] A. Giannopoulos, S. Spantideas, and P. Trakadas, "Spatiotemporal graph coloring for frequency assignment in spectrum-constrained ground-air-sea networks," *Authorea Preprints*, 2025.
- [17] F. Capulli, C. Monti, M. Vari, and F. Mazzenga, "Path loss models for ieee 802.11 a wireless local area networks," in *2006 3rd International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems*. IEEE, 2006, pp. 621–624.
- [18] H.-S. Park, H. Kim, C. Lee, and H. Lee, "Mobility management paradigm shift: From reactive to proactive handover using ai/ml," *IEEE Network*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 18–25, 2024.
- [19] Y. Zheng, S. Ren, X. Xu, Y. Si, M. Dong, and J. Wu, "A modified arima model for cqi prediction in lte-based mobile satellite communications," in *2012 IEEE International Conference on Information Science and Technology*, 2012, pp. 822–826.
- [20] Y. Feng, L. Liu, and J. Shu, "A link quality prediction method for wireless sensor networks based on xgboost," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 155 229–155 241, 2019.